

Periodical Dynamics of Live Weight of Sheep in the Conditions of Karakalpakstan

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Abstract:

The article highlights the results of studies on the dynamics of live weight of rams and ewes of different helical types in different periods of the year.

Keywords: Karakul ewes, rams, different periods, live weight, helical types, dynamics.

Karakul breeding is an important branch of animal husbandry, which develops mainly in desert areas and produces valuable agricultural products. Karakul breeding is developed in the extreme weather conditions of the desert, and Karakul sheep are kept on pastures all year round.

Like other farm animals, there is a relationship between productivity and live weight of Karakul sheep. The live weight of sheep at birth and later is important in determining their subsequent productivity.

Factors affecting growth indicators of sheep have been studied by many researchers. The nutritional productivity of desert pastures, grazing methods, constitutional, ethological and productivity characteristics affect the growth indicators, and it is important to take these data into account in breeding [1, 2, 3, 4, 9].

Positive results have been achieved through the use of various feeds and probiotics in improving the growth performance of sheep [5, 6, 7].

Based on the above, research was conducted in the direction of studying the dynamics of changes in the live weight of rams and ewes belonging to different helical types in different seasons in the conditions of Karakalpakstan.

Material and methods. The researches were carried out on black-colored Karakul sheep bred at the production enterprise "Ustyurt Karakul breeding Center" of Kungirov district of the Republic of Karakalpakstan.

The live weight of rams of different ages and ewes of helical type (in spring, summer and autumn) and its dynamics were determined by measuring on an electronic scale.

Biometric processing of the obtained data was carried out by the variational statistics method [10].

Results and their analysis. In the research, live weight indicators of rams and ewes belonging to different helical types in different seasons in the conditions of Karakalpakstan were determined and presented in Table 1 below.

Table 1. Periodic dynamics of live weight of sheep in the conditions of Karakalpakstan

Groups	n	Live weight, kg					
		Spring (April)		Summer (July)		Autumn (September)	
		X±Sx	Cv	X±Sx	Cv	X±Sx	Cv
Rams	30	42,8±0,43	5,51	51,9±0,54 ^{x)}	4,15	58,4±0,57 ^{x)}	5,35
Ewes							
Semicircle kalamgul	30	34,2±0,35 ^{x)}	5,61	39,4±0,42 ^{x)}	5,84	43,2±0,44 ^{x)}	7,62
Rib-shaped	30	34,5±0,37 ^{x)}	5,40	38,2±0,4 ^{x)}	5,88	42,9±0,42 ^{x)}	7,32
Flat	30	34,1±0,32 ^{x)}	5,14	37,9±0,39 ^{x)}	5,64	42,1±0,41 ^{x)}	7,38
Osikgul	30	36,7±0,38	5,74	41,2±0,44	5,85	44,5±0,45	7,56
Average	120	34,87±0,24 ^{x)}	7,54	39,17±0,21 ^{x)}	5,87	43,18±0,28 ^{x)}	7,10

x)-P<0,05

x)-P<0,001

It can be seen from the data in the table that there are changes in the live weight of rams and ewes in the cross section of the seasons. In particular, the live weight of rams was 42.8 kg in the spring season, compared to this period, the live weight was 9.1 kg higher in the summer season, and 15.6 kg in the autumn season.

Live weight indicators in ewes were studied not only in the cross-section of seasons, but also in the cross-section of helical types. The results show that the highest rate was observed in Osikgul type ewes in spring, which was 36.7 kg. Ewes of other helical types had higher live weight by 2.5, 2.2 and 2.6 kg respectively. This situation was also observed in summer and autumn seasons. The live weight of the osikgul variety was 1.9 kg higher than the average of the groups. Also, rib-shaped ewes had a live weight close to the average, while semicircle kalamgul ewes had a live weight close to the average in autumn. All observed differences were found to be statistically significant (x-P<0.05; x)-P<0.001).

In conclusion, it was found that the live weight of rams increased from spring to autumn, and live weight of ewes in the cross-section of helical types, it was found that the live weight of osikgul type ewes was higher.

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